
Incorporating Essential Criteria into Microbiological Risk Assessment: A Comprehensive Approach for the Food Industry

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ABSTRACT

The Microbiological Risk Assessment (MRA) is an integral part of food safety management in the food industry. This review aims to introduce an enhanced MRA model that incorporates essential criteria based on the Bradford Hill criteria for causality. By integrating these criteria into a decision tree framework, the model aims to offer a more rigorous and evidence-based approach to hazard identification and risk characterization. Preliminary applications of this model suggest its potential for improving the accuracy and reliability of MRA in food processing environments.

Keywords: Microbiological Risk Assessment, Food Safety, Hazard Identification, Hazard Characterization, Risk Characterization, Exposure Assessment, Foodborne Illness, Pathogen Screening, Risk Scoring, Risk Management

INTRODUCTION

Microbiological risk assessment (MRA) serves as a cornerstone in the management of food safety, particularly in food processing environments. However, the complexity and variability of foodborne pathogens often make traditional MRA methods inadequate. This paper seeks to present an enhanced MRA model, which incorporates essential criteria, providing a comprehensive and evidence-based approach to improve food safety measures.

Background

1. Microbiological Hazards in Food Processing

Microbiological hazards, such as bacteria, viruses, and fungi, pose a significant risk in food production. These hazards can lead to foodborne illnesses that may result in hospitalizations and even death.

2. Role of Risk Assessment in Food Safety

Risk assessment methodologies, often encapsulated within the Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points

(HACCP) system, provide a structured approach to identifying, evaluating, and controlling food safety hazards.

3. Traditional MRA Framework

The traditional MRA framework follows a four-step process: Hazard Identification, Hazard Characterization, Exposure Assessment, and Risk Characterization. However, this model often lacks the rigor needed for complex food processing environments.

4. Limitations and Challenges

Current MRA methodologies often fall short in adequately addressing all potential risks, largely due to a lack of comprehensive data and the nuanced understanding required for microbial behavior in different food matrices.

The Enhanced MRA Model

1. Decision Tree Framework

The enhanced MRA model employs a decision tree framework that builds upon the traditional four-step

process. It aims to streamline hazard identification by providing a structured pathway for decision-making. This decision tree is adaptable to various food products and processing methods, making it a versatile tool for food safety managers.

2. Incorporation of Essential Criteria

The novel aspect of this model is the incorporation of Essential Criteria, derived from the Bradford Hill criteria for causality. These criteria provide a more rigorous scientific basis for the decisions made at each step of the MRA, from hazard identification to risk characterization.

The Essential Criteria: A Closer Look

The Essential Criteria, based on the Bradford Hill criteria, are integrated into the decision tree to ensure a comprehensive and evidence-based approach. Each criterion is evaluated using a binary scoring system (0 for 'No', 1 for 'Yes'). A summarized score is then used to determine the significance of the hazard, with certain criteria serving as mandatory inclusions for the risk assessment.

Strength: Measures the strength of the relationship between the food-hazard pair and illness outcomes.

Consistency: Evaluates multiple observations of a hazard's likely occurrence in a food product.

Specificity: Considers the specificity of the illness to the food-hazard pair.

Temporality: Establishes that exposure to the hazard precedes the onset of illness.

Dose-Response: Assesses the relationship between the level of hazard exposure and the risk of illness.

Plausibility: Evaluates the biological plausibility of the hazard causing illness.

Coherence: Ensures that the food-hazard pair aligns with current scientific understanding.

Experimental Evidence: Incorporates experimental data, such as animal studies or prevalence studies.

Analogy: Takes into account similar hazards or similar foods known to contain the hazard.

Methodology

To apply the enhanced MRA model, practitioners can follow a series of steps:

Data Collection: Compile data from various sources, including scientific literature, in-house testing, and outbreak databases.

Hazard Identification: Utilize the decision tree to identify potential hazards.

Criteria Evaluation: Apply the Essential Criteria to evaluate the significance of each identified hazard.

Risk Characterization: Use the aggregated score from the Essential Criteria evaluation to characterize the risk level of each hazard.

One of the defining features of the enhanced MRA model is the incorporation of a decision tree that serves as a practical tool for food safety managers and practitioners. Below is a textual description of the decision tree.

Decision Tree Description

The decision tree is divided into four main steps:

Initial Hazard Identification: The tree starts with an initial screening question that filters out microorganisms not associated with foodborne illnesses.

Application of Essential Criteria: The second stage involves the application of the nine Essential Criteria. Each criterion is assessed on a binary scale (Yes/No = 1/0).

Score and Evaluate: The 'Yes' responses from the Essential Criteria are summed. Additionally, certain criteria may be considered mandatory for inclusion, requiring separate evaluation.

Decision: Based on the score and the evaluation of any mandatory criteria, a decision is made on whether to include the microorganism in the MRA.

Practical Implications

The decision tree serves as a systematic yet flexible tool for hazard identification, offering a more nuanced approach to MRA that accounts for various complexities in food processing environments.

Decision Tree for Enhanced Microbiological Risk Assessment

Step 1: Initial Hazard Identification

1. Is the pathogen associated with the raw material? If the pathogen is not found in the raw materials, it may be excluded from the MRA.
2. Is the pathogen known to survive or grow during processing? Some pathogens may be eliminated or reduced during food processing. If a pathogen is killed or reduced to safe levels, it may be excluded.
3. Does the final product provide conditions for pathogen survival? If the final product's conditions (e.g., pH, water activity) do not allow for the pathogen's survival, it may be excluded.
4. Is there a potential for re-contamination after control points? Re-contamination can occur at various stages after initial processing. If there's no such risk, the pathogen may not need to be considered.
5. Does the product have a history of being implicated in outbreaks? If the pathogen has been previously linked to outbreaks connected to the product, it is prudent to include it in the MRA.

If a pathogen makes it through all these questions, it should be included in the MRA for a more detailed analysis and proceed to Step 2, if it does not, it can be excluded from further assessment.

Graphical Representation

Step 2: Apply Essential Criteria

Strength: Is there a strong link between the food-hazard pair and acute or chronic illnesses, supported by outbreaks or case-control studies? Yes/No

Consistency: Have there been multiple observations,

such as recalls or positive test results, indicating the likelihood of the hazard being present in the food?
Yes/No

Specificity: Is there evidence that a particular population developed illness following exposure, with no other plausible explanation for the illness? Yes/No

Temporality: Is there evidence showing that exposure to the food-hazard pair precedes the onset of acute or chronic illnesses, supported by outbreaks, sporadic cases, or cohort studies? Yes/No

Dose-Response: Is there a direct relationship between increasing levels of exposure to the hazard and the risk of acute or chronic illnesses? Yes/No

Plausibility: Is it biologically plausible that the hazard could be present in the food and/or cause acute or chronic illness? Yes/No

Coherence: Does the food-hazard pair align with current understanding of the food supply and food safety? Yes/No

Experimental Evidence: Is there experimental evidence linking the microorganism to foodborne illness? Yes/No

Analogy: Is there a similar hazard that is supported by the food (e.g., if STEC O157 is a known hazard, consider non-O157 STEC as well), or is a similar food known to contain the hazard (e.g., Cyclospora in raspberries and strawberries)? Yes/No

Step 3: Score and Evaluate

Calculate the sum of 'Yes' responses from Step 2.

If any Essential Criteria are considered as mandatory for inclusion (e.g., 'Strength' or 'Temporality'), evaluate those separately.

Step 4: Decision

If the score meets or exceeds a predefined threshold, or if any mandatory Essential Criteria are met, include the microorganism in the MRA.

The use of a numerical scoring system based on the

Bradford Hill criteria could provide a more quantifiable method for decision-making in Microbiological Risk Assessment (MRA). However, it's crucial to recognize that not all criteria may carry the same weight or importance depending on the specific context of the food and hazard in question.

If you assign a value of 0 for 'No' and 1 for 'Yes' for each of the nine Bradford Hill criteria, the maximum score would be 9.

Options for Minimum Score

Conservative Approach: A conservative approach might consider a lower threshold, such as a score of 5 or 6 out of 9, as a minimum for including a hazard in the MRA. This approach would be more inclusive and may capture hazards that are emerging or less well-understood.

Moderate Approach: A more moderate approach might set the threshold at 7, ensuring that a majority of the criteria are met.

Stringent Approach: A stringent approach might require a higher score, such as 8 or 9, to include a hazard. This would likely only capture hazards that are well-supported by existing evidence but might exclude emerging or less well-documented hazards.

Considerations

Context-Specific: The minimum score could be adjusted based on the specific context, the population at risk, and regulatory guidelines.

Critical Criteria: Some criteria might be considered critical and therefore non-negotiable. For example, 'Temporality', 'Strength' and 'Experimental Evidence' might be essential to establish a causal relationship.

Temporality: If it is unequivocally established that exposure to the hazard precedes the illness, this criterion could be pivotal for inclusion in the MRA.

Strength: If there is a strong and well-established link between the food-hazard pair and acute or chronic illnesses, this could be considered a critical criterion.

Experimental Evidence: If there is definitive experimental proof that the hazard causes the illness in question, this could be another critical criterion.

Expert Consultation: It might be beneficial to consult with epidemiologists, microbiologists, and other experts to determine the most appropriate minimum score for your specific situation.

Regulatory Guidelines: Ensure that any scoring system aligns with local, national, or international regulations and guidelines.

A numerical approach based on the Bradford Hill criteria could provide a systematic, replicable method for hazard inclusion, but it should be applied thoughtfully and in accordance with the specific risk context and regulatory landscape.

Discussion

1. Advantages of the Enhanced MRA Model

The enhanced MRA model offers several advantages, including increased scientific rigor, adaptability to different food products, and a more nuanced approach to risk characterization.

2. Potential Limitations and Mitigations

While the model offers a more comprehensive approach, it is not without limitations. For instance, the binary scoring system may oversimplify complex relationships. However, the Essential Criteria serve as a counterbalance, providing depth and nuance to the evaluation.

3. Regulatory Implications

The enhanced model aligns well with global food safety standards, such as those outlined by the GFSI and WHO/FAO, offering a robust method that can stand up to regulatory scrutiny.

4. Practical Applications in Food Processing

The model is particularly useful in complex food processing environments where traditional MRA methods may fall short. It allows for a more targeted

allocation of resources to high-risk areas, enhancing overall food safety.

Conclusions

The enhanced MRA model provides a robust, evidence-based framework for microbiological risk assessment in the food industry. By integrating Essential Criteria into the decision tree framework, the model offers a comprehensive approach that addresses the limitations of traditional MRA methods.

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